

THE IMPACT OF ADCCB PROGRAMS IN PROMOTING FINANCIAL INCULSION

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ABSTRACT

Despite all the efforts and initiatives put in place by GOI, RBI, NABARD and Other development finance institutions to improve financial inclusion, there is huge Concern to GOI and RBI and other development partners because it hinders inclusive economic growth. The study investigates to what extent the ADCCB financial programs playing vital role in promoting financial inclusion in adilabad district. The study is central axis developing model that explains the employees opinion in financial inclusion through various schemes of GOI, RBI and other factors. The main aim of current study indicates that the programs for promoting the financial products is positively and significantly related to financial inclusion, for the study we have taken 50 respondents/ bank employees of ADCCB of adilabad district, and data analysis was performed by adoptin stastical tools and multivariient techniques to know the level of signficance to test the association between the ADCCB programs and its impact on financial inclusion. The implications of the main finding of this study are important because they highlights and focus areas for policy makers to achieve optional results in financial inclusion.

Keywords: ADCCB, GOI, RBI, NABARD, Financial Inclusion.

I. INTRODUCTION

India occupies twenty four percent of the world's land area and constitutes more than sixteen percent of the world's population. Nearly about seventy three percent of the Indian population lives in villages and engages in agricultural activities but are not earning profit because of lack of knowledge depending on seasons. Lack of technology and other reasons rural development has to play important role in the socio-economic development of the country. Like India where the majority of the people live in rural areas. As Gandhi said, "Real India lies in the village" and the village economy is the backbone of the Indian economy without development of the rural economy, 'the objective of the economic planning cannot be achieved.' The development of the nation completely depends on the rural economy, the objective of the economic planning cannot be achieved without impotance for development of rural economy. The development of the nation completely depends on the rural economy. Many studies and government report reveals rural population is excluded from financial services; this has been directly impacting rural people who are remaining poor. The government of India has taken many initiatives in respect of financial inclusion programs, so that cooperative banks have been introduced, to empower the rural people financially good. The objective of the co-operative bank is to provide financial services to needy people at an affordable cost, and it plays an important role in rural financing. The Co-operative banks are acting as a platform to solve the problems of rural people. This study mainly focused on the role of ADCCB (Adilabad District Co-operative central bank Ltd., in promoting financial inclusion, with respect to the development of the District economy and to providing various financial services to less fortunate people.

Rural development is always an important issue in all decisions about economic development especially in developing countries like India, throughout the world. In India, the agriculture sector is not, profitable because rural people depend on the monsoon and the lack of infrastructure and technology and some other reasons. Therefore, it leads to industrial backwardness.

In Adilabad district, the rural people are very poor, they depend on the monsoon, they cultivate small crops for their survival. They do not have enough money and even they do not approach any bank for borrowing. They are illiterate; they do not have insurance facilities. The central government and state government are providing different schemes but they do not aware of any type of schemes provided by the government.

Finance is an important requirement for the rural people, co-operative banks are an integral part of the Indian rural economy and cooperative banks have a direct and indirect impact on agricultural growth and rural development.

In this connection, the cooperative bank is providing loan facilities to these rural farmers. The business of co-operative banks is also increased in the rural areas due to primary agriculture co-operative societies. These societies work for DCCBS in rural areas.

FINANCIAL INCLUSION:

Financial inclusion is a method of offering banking and financial services to individuals. It aims to make inclusion every person in society by giving them basic financial services and it focuses on providing financial solutions to the economically underprivileged. Financial inclusion is the subject that plays a major role to empower the rural people.

RURAL DEVELOPMENT:

There is a necessity for rural development and this arises due to the gap between urban and rural areas in terms of infrastructural facility, and their income. Rural development which implies the small farmer's agriculture progress encompasses efforts to raise both farm and non-farm rural people income through job creation, rural industrialization and increased provision of education. The countries large share of revenue is contributed by the rural sector, which provide food to the entire population and raw material to materials to agree-based industries. For this reason, rural finance plays a vital role in the development of rural areas. It started lending money in informal sector through money lenders, relatives, and institutional credit facilities, commercial banks, cooperative banks, land development banks and government in the developing countries like India, with regional imbalances.

ADCCB:

The co-operative banks are government-backed financial institutions that work on the principle of co-operative. The cooperative banks are mainly set up to provide access to credit in rural areas. This empowers and secures the poor people and the low-income groups. Co-operative banks offer basic banking services in rural and urban areas, where banking facilities are scarce cooperative banks helps and encourage rural business and agriculture sector and work towards growth. The objectives of co-operative banks: Co-operative banks provide credit facilities like rural financing and micro-financing. Co-operative banks aim to offer credit to the command men at low-interest rates, eliminating the dominance of private money lenders. Providing agriculture loans at a low-interest rate to farmers for the growth of the agriculture sector and allied activities. Provide easy access to finance for rural industries providing financial services in rural areas where banking facilities are scarce, helping the poor and low-income group farmers.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Raman, A. (2012). Financial inclusion and growth of the Indian banking system. The difficulty of monetary inclusion is rising as the new paradigm of financial growth. Financial inclusion performs a fundamental function in using away from poverty from the country. Financial inclusion refers to the shipping of banking offerings to loads which include privileged and deprived humans at less expensive phrases and conditions. It now not solely enhances the common monetary depth of agriculture however additionally helps in growing rural non-farm things to do which lead to the improvement of the rural economic system and enhance the monetary situation of people. The three primary elements of economic inclusion are (i) get admission to monetary market (ii) get right of entry to savings market (iii) study monetary matters. Reserve financial institution of India and the authorities play an vital function in merchandising economic inclusion for monetary growth. The authorities and RBI have taken a number of steps to amplify banking penetration in the country, nationalization of banks, the institution of RRBs, the introduction of SHG and the method of one character one account for gaining access to the economic market. Accessing savings amenities enhancing activity rates, easy KYC manner are principal steps due to the fact almost 80% of the populace in India is besides life, health, nonlife insurance plan cover. RBI has additionally adopted two techniques to generate notable consciousness and extend the attain of banking offerings which can be termed empowerment and protection. The current paper motive is to get admission to the Indian ride thru descriptive and empirical research of on hand statistical information and the function of RBI in merchandising economic inclusion. With exceptional reference to some articles, it is discovered that there are 403 million cell customers in India of which 54% has a financial institution account. Which rural common amongst the person populace is 39% in opposition to 60% in Urban India. Himachal Pradesh is the solely country to gain full monetary inclusion. The

paper additionally explains the similar opportunities, scope and challenges for monetary inclusion. The paper concludes that economic inclusion performs a primary function in riding away poverty from the country. In India, a day will come when all Indians have their financial institution money owed and every person will take section in monetary inclusion.

Bharadi, H. H. (2013). Role of the banking sector and financial inclusion. The focus of economic policy in India has shifted to issues of equitable distribution of growth. The economy should maintain the tempo of economic growth but also spread the benefits of growth to all sections of the population and geographical regions of the country. Financial inclusion is identified as a key strategy to achieve inclusive development in all sections of society. It is a necessary condition for financial deepening, which will address the basic issue of growth with equity in India. Apart from addressing the issue of inequality, financial inclusion may also make the poverty reduction efforts more effective by explicitly creating productive economic opportunities for the poor and vulnerable sections of society. Inclusive growth by encompassing the hitherto excluded population can bring in several other benefits to all in the economy. Supply-side and demand-side factors are driving Inclusive Growth. Banks and other financial services players are expected to mitigate the supply side processes that prevent poor and disadvantaged social groups from gaining access to the financial system, apart from the supply side factors, the demand-side factors, such as lower-income and asset holdings also have a significant bearing on inclusive growth, financial stability, economic stability and inclusive growth with stability are an important objective of the government, it is not possible without achieving financial inclusion. Hence, the present study is undertaken on some of the supply-side institutions and their role in mitigating the economic problems in India through financial inclusion.

Karmakar, K. G., Banerjee, G. D., & Mohapatra, N. P. (2011). Towards financial inclusion in India. The focal point of monetary coverage in India has shifted to problems of equitable distribution of growth. The financial system must hold the tempo of monetary boom however additionally unfold the advantages of increase to all sections of the populace and geographical areas of the country. Financial inclusion is recognized as a key method to acquire inclusive improvement in all sections of society. It is an integral circumstance for economic deepening, which will tackle the simple difficulty of boom with fairness in India. Apart from addressing the difficulty of inequality, economic inclusion may additionally additionally make the poverty discount efforts extra fantastic with the aid of explicitly growing productive financial possibilities for the terrible and prone sections of society. Inclusive increase by way of encompassing the hitherto excluded populace can carry in a number of different advantages to all in the economy. Supply-side and demand-side elements are using Inclusive Growth. Banks and different economic offerings gamers are anticipated to mitigate the grant facet strategies that stop bad and deprived social agencies from gaining get right of entry to to the monetary system, aside from the provide facet factors, the demand-side factors, such as lower-income and asset holdings additionally have a extensive bearing on inclusive growth, monetary stability, financial steadiness and inclusive boom with balance are an necessary goal of the government, it is now not feasible barring reaching economic inclusion. Hence, the current learn about is undertaken on some of the supply-side establishments and their position in mitigating the financial issues in India via economic inclusion.

Ravikumar, T. (2012). Role of banks in financial inclusion process in India. Access to cheap monetary offerings – in unique credit score and insurance plan graph – enlarges livelihood chances and empowers human beings to take price of their lives. Such empowerment aids the social inclusion of such bad humans and affords political stability. Financial inclusion imparts formal identity, affords get right of entry to to rate constructions and brings terrible human beings into monetary savings and security net. Hence, economic inclusion is viewed to be integral for accomplishing inclusive growth of the Indian economy. India has the second-largest financially one-of-a-kind populace in the world, totally subsequent to China. As per National Sample Survey Organization's (NSSO) Survey (59th round), in the commonplace category, 51.4% of farmer households are financially excluded from every formal and informal sources. Of the entire farmer households, totally 27% have get admission to to formal sources of credit, one-third of this group moreover borrow from non-formal sources. Region-wise, the exclusion is most acute in Central, Eastern and North-Eastern areas – having a awareness of 64% of all financially excluded farmer households in the country. Moreover, completely 59% of the man or woman populace in the u . s . a . has a monetary institution account and 41% of the populace is unbanked. In rural areas, the insurance is 39% in opposition to 69% in town areas. The extent of exclusion from credit score

is heaps more. Several personal loan bills constituted completely 14% of the grownup population. In rural areas, the insurance plan is 9.5% toward 14% in metropolis areas. These types of financial exclusion of low-income human beings are the constraints for the improvement of any financial system in specific a growing monetary device like India. This article tries to look at the characteristic of banks in the financial inclusion technique in India with the help of reachable data.

Study Objectives

The aim of this study is:

- To understand the concept of financial inclusion.
- To what extent the ADCCB programs playing vitale role in promoting Financial Inusion in Adilabad District.

Study Hypothesis

- The ADCCB Programs for promoting financial inclusion do not have significant level of impact on the people of different areas in the study region.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This is an empirical study based on the survey method of the interview schedule. The data was used to collect both primary and secondary sources..From Adilabad district some ADCCB branches are selected. In each branch 5 employees to the sample selected and this comprises a total of 50 employees, convenience sampling technique to used with the help of structured interview schedule to collect the relevant data.

In this research, a well-structured questionnaire and interview schedule are used to collect the primary data from 50 respondents of ADCCB.

Data Analysis:

This sample of fifty respondents contains 32 male and 18 female respondents which make-up for 64 and 36 percentage respectively. The largest group of respondents that is (66%) with Gradate or higher the smallest group of respondents (10%) with a up to secondary leaving the rest of 24% with a up to senior secondary. 36% of the respondents are with (31-40) years of old while 8% above 50 years of old leaving the remaining into other smaller years of age. Based on the objectives and hypotheses of the study, the researchers applied the ANOVA test at 5% level of significance to test the association between the ADCCB programs and its impact on financial inclusion promoted.

ANOVA

	df	F	Sig.
Programs for promoting financial inclusion	2	6.642	.003
	47		
	49		

The statistical output showed a p-value of 0.003 which is less than 0.05 and hence Null hypothesis is Rejected. ANOVA test proved that, “The ADCCB Programs for promoting financial inclusion do not have a significant level of impact on the people of different areas in the study region”.

IV. FINDINGS

This observation enables me to conclude that, “The ADCCB programs have the ability in promoting the financial inclusion in Adilabad.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper aims to build a more complete framework of the factors, which influence on the financial inclusion,of ADCCB in Adilabad district. This research contributes to the understanding of the financial inclusion and financial literacy. It describes an integration of financial inclusion and the programs provided by ADCCB. I hope that these conclusions will shed some light for top management and allowing them to increase attention and more improve for their programs.

VI. REFERENCES

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